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Semantic Census: Sustainable Semantic Data Management Pipeline Documentation

Semantic Census Deliverable 4: An ETL pipeline from easydb to RDF
Semantic Census Deliverable 6: Semantic Data Transformation and Testing

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Executive Summary

This document outlines the semantic data management pipeline developed and set up for the Semantic Census project as an integral part with the data transformation and testing phase. The pipeline is a series of steps related to different tools and software which acts at once as:

- a method to support the semantic transformation of the extant Census data, managed in FYLR, into a CIDOC CRM compatible RDF format
- a general process model for the transformation of related art and architecture historical data into a compatible semantic data model

This document will outline the methodology of the proposed pipeline and provide a starting point for the reuse of the presently instantiated pipeline. The contents of this document meet the goals set out in deliverables defined in two integrally connected work packages (WPs).

WP 4 (Pipeline development) consisted in the development of an ETL pipeline, that enables the replicable transformation of the Census data from easydb into a semantic RDF representation to be made available in a repository for reuse by other researchers. The pipeline includes the necessary steps to export data from the easydb, run automated transformations to prepare the data for use in the mapping engine, the provision of mapping files and the setup of the transformation engine to create the output RDF. The documentation of this process and procedure was compiled as Deliverable 4.

Deliverable 6 was completed as a result of the work in work package 5 (WP5). WP5 consisted in running transformations of the easydb data to RDF using the mapping files and ETL pipeline under development as a part of WP4. The transformation tests were used to

- a) gauge the accuracy of the transformation in the first place (semantic data quality) and
- b) test the adequacy of the transformed system to answer baseline queries relative to the Census data. It allows for quality control of the generated semantic Census data and to begin to explore the derivation of more advanced research questions using the semantic graph. This process allows us to work on potential issues in advance before the final stage of the project. In addition to quality testing, this phase will allow for a chance to test the data against more complicated research questions, through a collaboration between Takin.solutions and the Census team to develop a set of competence questions, that will demonstrate the capability of the semantic network to address more complicated research questions analytically at the end of WP4.

As a prerequisite to the testing process Takin has set up a triplestore testing space for working testing and exploring the data in WP6.

Introduction

The goal of creating the semantic data pipeline was to create both an initial transform of the Census data into a semantic format and to make this process repeatable in order to encourage further integration of the Census data with other datasets over time. The generation of semantic data from existing data sources is an intellectually and technologically intensive activity which requires an investment of time and resources in order to accomplish. Making sure that this process is repeatable is a way of making this activity sustainable and to promote its benefits through the further uptake of this method. Generating a sustainable semantic data pipeline is key to the long term utility of Semantic Census to become part of a wider scholarly project which takes advantage of the semantic linked open data.

Two key factors must be taken into account in order to create a sustainable semantic data pipeline.

- Documentation of Process
- Use of Open Source Tooling

The first factor is often the most overlooked. While many semantic projects are created to cover one area or another, the means by which they arrive at their results, ensuring repeatability and reusability, are most often not captured. The second factor is also very important. In the context of an academic environment, the use of open source tools that provide easy uptake and which are well maintained is an important element in keeping the data workflows described available and implementable.

This document, which describes both the process used by the Semantic Census project, as well as the open source tooling actually put into use to achieve its results, aims to take these two important factors into account as main concerns.

In order to support the description of a reusable semantic data pipeline for Semantic Census data, the following large scale steps were envisioned:

- Process Tracking
- Conceptual Modelling and Documentation
- Conceptual Mapping and Implemented Mapping Documentation
- Extract Transform and Load Process

The body of this document will outline what each of these stages entail in general and how they were practically carried out in this project, providing a recipe for reuse into the future.

Process Tracking

As will be reiterated numerous times in this document, semantic data management is an investment which must be made sustainable if it is to become an integrated part of a more general academic workflow rather than a one-off exercise. Semantic data processing and transformation is about taking control of the meaning of data and how it can be expressed and interrogated. It takes seriously the value as primary data of the information curated and maintained in professional research databases. The Census project with its curated content of over 40 years of research is a perfect test and proof for this general aim.

A basic step in maintaining data before any others is simply to have a catalogue of what data one has, where it is and to what data processes it is related to in the first place. This somewhat obvious step is nevertheless very often overlooked.

Without such a management function, however, it is difficult to understand the state of one's data. Knowing the overall territory of data, however, is essential for doing semantic data management, as it is necessary to know what data is being generated and what it means, and who to ask about it in particular if it is unclear. Moreover, for controlling the flow of data in a semantic data pipeline one needs to understand the present state of curation and transformation of source data and the location of mapping files, output files and final outputs.

Method

For all of the above reasons, one needs at least a basic tracking system of data sources and their function in the semantic data pipeline processes.

While there are complex semantic models for representing data sources and their relations including Prov-O¹ and CRMpe², *inter alia*, it was assessed that what was required for this project was a straightforward data management tool which would organise in a linear fashion the relations between the different semantic data management processing steps.

We decided to create a basic register using a spreadsheet that would map to the different stages of the semantic data pipeline process and enable the tracking of the linear progression of the semantic data process from initial data modelling to final ETL.

Tooling

We adopted google spreadsheets as a straightforward adoptable tool with well known functions and easy sharing functionality. The data schema drawn up reflects the steps of the semantic data management pipeline outlined in this document. It can be accessed [here](#).

¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

² <https://zenodo.org/record/2575465>

Conclusion

The adoption of a semantic data management process tracker allows an easy overview of the data under consideration in a project and its relation to data models, data mappings and data outputs. It significantly aids in generating an overview understanding of the state of play of the semantic data process and is extensible meaning that future data projects can pick up from this baseline pattern and extend it while relating back to work already done.

Conceptual Modelling and Documentation

The basis of a semantic data project is the adoption and application of a formal ontology for the description of the data in question. The point of creating semantic data, either from scratch or from existing data sources, is to be able to explicitly represent the meaning of the data contained within traditional data structures in a generic way, understandable to other researchers/scientists as well as to developers. The data is formatted in precise S-V-O sentences generated under a controlled vocabulary of classes and properties, corresponding approximately to generic nouns and verbs of a natural language. The semantic data format aims to bridge a communication gap between researchers and technologists, creating a machine readable *lingua franca* that can be used as a point of reference by both communities. Typically, to ensure compatibility with other potential datasets and in order to speed development time, it is wise to adopt an existing top level ontology with which to model one's data if that exists.

Conceptual modelling is the prefiguration of ideal data patterns in a semantic space that cover the kinds of statements (information points) that researchers aim to be able to record, query and visualise with regards to different real world entities that are their objects of research.

In the Semantic Census data pipeline, the first step was the creation of the conceptual models that would cover the dataspace discussed within the scope of the Census data.

To this end the first step was to choose both a formal ontology for describing the Census data as well as a conceptual modelling strategy for deploying that ontology. We chose the CIDOC CRM³ as the obvious choice given its wide acceptance across different cultural heritage research communities as shown by its adoption in large scale EU H2020 projects and in data modelling communities from museum professionals to historians. For a data modelling strategy, using CIDOC CRM, we chose to follow the Swiss Art Research Infrastructure Semantic Reference Data Models⁴. These patterns were chosen because of their adoption by potential partner institutions to the Census data especially within the CORDH network⁵ including the Hertziana⁶, a one time home of the Census itself.

This stage of the pipeline should have as a result a solid set of semantic data models that are fully documented which will represent the target data structure in this and future semantic data transformations of Census or Census related data into a common semantic format.

Method

Our goal was to adopt the most widely acceptable semantic patterns as possible and to generate as few new patterns as possible, while staying true to the semantic valence of the actual Census data.

³ <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

⁴ <https://docs.swissartresearch.net/>

⁵ <https://www.cordh.net/>

⁶ <https://www.biblhertz.it/en/home>

In order to do this, we began from the set of semantic data patterns provided by the SARI SRDMs. These provide a set of established and validated semantic patterns for a number of basic entities in the documentation world. In particular these include:

- Person
- Artwork
- Group
- Builtwork
- Event
- Digital Object
- Bibliographic Item
- Place
- Archival Unit
- Image
- Information Carrier

A semantic analysis was then carried out of the tables of data in the Census dataset. The following tables were identified for modelling:

- Monument
- Document
- Person
- Location
- Image
- Period
- Style
- Bibliography

The extant structure of the Census data which placed the documentation of date at the centre of its strategy for the integration of information regarding the reception of antiquity in the renaissance made the data particularly amenable to re-expression as semantic data models.

The outcome of this activity was the creation of the following ideal semantic data models for describing the Census data:

Model Name	CRM Class	Link
Monument	E22 Human-Made Object	https://zellij.pythonanywhere.com/docs/display/appmG43hOvEy3KYTX/Model?search=MOD.CEN.1 Monument
Document	E22 Human-Made Object	https://zellij.pythonanywhere.com/docs/display/appmG43hOvEy3KYTX/Model?search=MOD.CEN.2 Document

Person	E21 Person	https://zellij.pythonanywhere.com/docs/display/appmG43hOvEy3KYTX/Model?search=MOD.CEN.3_Person
Location	E53 Place	https://zellij.pythonanywhere.com/docs/display/appmG43hOvEy3KYTX/Model?search=MOD.CEN.5_Location
Image	E36/D9 Image	Visual https://zellij.pythonanywhere.com/docs/display/appmG43hOvEy3KYTX/Model?search=MOD.CEN.8_Image
Period / Style	E4 Period	https://zellij.pythonanywhere.com/docs/display/appmG43hOvEy3KYTX/Model?search=MOD.CEN.6_Period
Bibliography	E33 Object	Linguistic https://zellij.pythonanywhere.com/docs/display/appmG43hOvEy3KYTX/Model?search=MOD.CEN.4_Bibliographic+Entity

Table 1. Census semantic data models

The details of this semantic modelling are discussed in D2 of this project available [here](#). Important to highlight here is what this semantic modelling achieves.

The above data models represent a complete, ideal representation of the semantic content of the Census data as it would be expressed in CIDOC CRM following the modelling strategy of the SARI SRDMs. This means that the project has a baseline semantic data standard of its own, aligned to a broader group, to act as a target for its future semantic data works. This means that the above Census Semantic Reference Data Models can be used by scholars and technologists to: understand that data of Semantic Census, query it, visualise and manipulate it. This is a significant achievement for sustainability in a semantic data project because it leaves behind a total record of the semantic strategy adopted for the data.

Typically semantic projects adopt an ontology in order to do all the documentation work. Since it is self describing this is viewed as sufficient. In actual fact, however, there is a significant gap between an ontology and its adoption for modelling and then mapping data that involves multiple non reductive decisions. By generating a complete documented target model to guide the semantic data pipeline for the Semantic Census, the baseline decision on the application of the ontology and its meanings are fully spelled out and made reusable to technologists and researchers to take advantage of.

Tooling

Achieving a rich and consistent documentation of the intended target model for semantic data management is an area of work receiving insufficient attention in the wider semantic data community. While tools abound to manage the creation and updating of ontologies themselves, there are few tools for documenting their use in deployment, with the most relevant being related to the documentation of semantic data patterns (Sowa 2006).

The Zellij tool, developed and maintained by Takin.solutions, however, provided a robust and convenient way to both support the semantic analysis of the Census data in the first place and then to generate Semantic Reference Data Models for the documentation of Semantic Census.

Technologically the system is built on a software stack of:

- Airtable (Fig. 1)
- Python Framework for Display - the Zellij tool (Fig. 2)

ID	Model	Field	Model_Specific_Collecti...	Model_Specific_Collection_Order	Model_Specific_Field_Order	Model_Specific
01_MOD.CEN.6_fie_5_Name	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_5_Name		01		Period Name
02_MOD.CEN.6_fie_10_Alternative_Name	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_10_Alternative Name		02		Period Alias
03_MOD.CEN.6_fie_11_Alternative_Name_Type	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_11_Alternative Name Type		03		Period Alias Type
04_MOD.CEN.6_fie_15_Alternative_Name_-_Attribute...	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_15_Alternative Name - Attr		04		Period Alias Attrib
05_MOD.CEN.6_fie_17_Type	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_17_Type		05		Period Type
06_MOD.CEN.6_fie_1_Identifier	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_1_Identifier		06		Period Identifier
07_MOD.CEN.6_fie_2_Identifier_Type	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_2_Identifier Type		07		Period Identifier T
08_MOD.CEN.6_fie_3_Identifier_Provider	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_3_Identifier Provider		08		Period Identifier P
09_MOD.CEN.6_fie_50_Earliest_Possible_End_Date	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_50_Earliest Possible End C		09		Period Earliest Po
10_MOD.CEN.6_fie_51_Latest_Possible_End_Date	MOD.CEN.6_Period	fie_51_Latest Possible End Da		10		Period Latest Pos

Figure 1. Airtable modelling of the Census data

The Zellij system provides the following functionalities

- Create, Edit, Interrelate Semantic Data Patterns
- Store and Share Semantic Data Patterns
- Present and Explain Semantic Data Patterns

66_MOD.CEN.2_fie_cen_32_parallel_or_copy_type	Document Relation Type	This field is used to record the type of similarity between the described document and another document.	--> P011 --> PC130[C31_1] --> P130.1 --> E55[C32_1]
67_MOD.CEN.2_fie_cen_31_parallel_or_copy	Document Relation	This field is used to record the type of similarity between the described document and another document.	--> P011 --> PC130[C31_1] --> P02 --> E22[C31_2]
68_MOD.CEN.2_fie_cen_56_type_cause_of_observation	Document Notes	This field is used to record a general statement about the described document.	--> P2 --> E55[C56_1] --> P2 --> E55[C56_2]
69_MOD.CEN.2_fie_196_Citation	Document Citation	This field is used to record a citation to reference documentation for the described document.	--> P129i --> E33[196_1] --> rdf:value --> rdfs:Literal --> P129i --> E33[196_1] --> P2 --> E55 "Citation"
70_MOD.CEN.2_fie_197_Citation_Source	Document Citation Source	This field is used to record the source used for generating the citation for the described document.	--> P129i --> E33[196_1] --> P106i --> E33[197_1]
71_MOD.CEN.2_fie_cen_13_bibliographic_reference	Document Bibliography	This field is used to record a bibliographic reference for the described document.	--> P67i --> E33[C13_1]
72_MOD.CEN.2_fie_195_Image	Document Image	This field is used to record a digital image which is representative of the described document.	--> P138i --> E36/D9[195_1]
73_MOD.CEN.2_fie_204_Same_As	Document URL	The field is used to record the sameness between the described document and an external authority	--> L54 --> E1[204_1]
74_MOD.CEN.2_fie_cen_57_url_title	Document URL Title	The field is used to record the sameness between the described document and an external authority.	--> L54 --> E1[204_1] --> P1 --> E33_E41[C57_1]

Figure 2. Zelij representation of the semantic data patterns

The data management and storage systems are supported through the airtable interface. The Semantic Census documentation is given its own Airtable base following the Zelij Schema. The Zelij schema enables the documentation of semantic patterns at the level of: field, collection and model.

The building block of the system is a field pattern. The field is a named and documented semantic pattern that expresses a unique path within an ontological frame. The unique ontological path goes from a domain semantic class through n semantic edges and nodes, to a determined end node (class or literal). The 'field' is given a human understandable label and description while also having its semantic patterns explicitly written out in RDF. This simple determination helps build a library of reusable, atomic semantic data patterns. Collections and Models adopt semantic fields in order to describe large semantic data patterns.

A collection represents a commonly documented cluster of real world information, which is considered together in documenting and understanding another entity. Examples would be: Name, Birth, Identifier information. Each of these areas of analysis or documentation are typically taken up not for their own sake but in relation to another entity. That said, a phenomenon like a name typically entails a complex of information that could only be described by multiple semantic paths (fields). To speak of name content, type, language etc. are all independent semantic expressions which nevertheless interrelate around a single intermediary node of information (in this case the name). So a collection allows that fields be grouped into larger units that illustrate typical documentation and data exploration patterns.

A model stands for a single class of real world entities that are a topic of documentation and investigation within a research context. Models are defined in order to pick out the real world entities that are of interest to document and research within a project and to define, via fields and collections, the set of information that is typically gathered around them. Models are the unit of data collection and instances of models are the subject of interrelation via semantic reference.

The above structure provides a more than robust system for describing the semantic shape of the Census data. Moreover, Zelij allows the sharing of semantic data patterns between projects. An additional technical motivation for adopting the SARI SRDMs included that projects use of the Zelij system as well for their semantic documentation. Having chose to adopt the SRDMs meant that we could reuse the semantic data patterns already outlined there focussing on creating only the essential new semantic data patterns.

The outcome of this process was the generation of

- 95 Fields
- 3 Collections
- 7 Models

The sustainability of the project itself is predicated on the model patterns built up through the SARI and Census semantic data fields, while the creation of the 95 new fields extending the SARI models offers a contribution back to the community of SARI model users.

The navigation and exploration of these are available directly through the python display framework [here](#).

The Zelij tool itself is built on a straightforward technology stack and is in further development at time of writing to adopt open source tooling for the backend and data entry interface. For the scope of this project the continued sustainability of the documentation generated from it was assured by exporting it into simple csv as well as into a complex markdown format supporting navigation and understandability and existing stand-alone from the main database. The documentation built with markdown was uploaded on github as a free repository and made available via gh-pages, later transferred to the official Census github account available [here](#).

Conclusion

The adoption of a robust and sustainable means to not only forge a strategy for semantically representing the census data but to document these decisions and link them to a wider community guided us to the use of the Zelij tool. This gave us a consistent and explicit semantics on which to organise the next phases of the semantic data management lifecycle, specially ETL and exploration.

Semantic Data Mapping

Having decided on a robust semantic data target model to represent one's data, any legacy content which should be so represented must be analysed and related to the semantic model through a semantic data mapping.

The semantic data mapping step is a step in the pipeline that often receives less recognition and documentation than it deserves. Mapping is the process of specifying how the contents of one schema structure relate to another schema structure. Semantic data mapping typically entails the specification of the relation between a non semantic source schema and a semantic target schema. Semantic data mapping can further be differentiated into a conceptual mapping and an implemented mapping. A conceptual mapping takes place at the level of knowledge representation using some representation tool: spreadsheet, diagram, document. It provides a schematic representation of how a source relates to a target. An implemented semantic mapping is the actual writing out of this mapping into a formal computer language such that these instructions can be used by a software programme to generate semantic data outputs. A conceptual semantic mapping is successful just in case the correlation of source to target preserves the propositional meaning that the user of the source system had in mind when generating data using their source data schema. An implemented semantic mapping is successful if it meets both the above criterion for semantic correctness and successfully transforms the source data into the target schema in a syntactically correct serialisation of that data in a particular format.

The semantic mapping of an extant data source creates a bridge between its original format and the desired semantic form. It is also the step at which the original data can either be properly understood and transformed, and achieve the goals above or confusingly misinterpreted resulting in difficult to understand and faulty incorrect data.

This is a step in the semantic data management process at which a great amount of time and resources can be misspent, if the process is not clear and the tools by which to communicate are not amenable to all parties. Parties to the conversation include the original data owners, who are those who can best interpret the original data, the conceptual modellers, who best understand and are able to interpret the target semantic data model and the developers who are responsible for developing the code that will move the data from the source to target.

Method

In order to meet the challenge of this step, we relied on the foundation built in the conceptual modelling step and the documentation of the Semantic Census model. We built up a two step process to reflect the conceptual phase of the semantic mapping and to easily transition to the implementation phase.

For the purposes of the conceptual phase of the mapping, we were able to reduce the exercise to a one to one mapping operation of the data fields of the census data model as implemented in FYLR to the semantic data field patterns which we developed in step 1. This

is to say that we innovated on the conceptual modelling process step by using reusable, named semantic data model patterns in order to describe the data model transition and pass it to the developers for implementation. This achieved significant economies of scale because the mapping processing becomes a simple 1:1 machining process of a name to name. This both creates efficiencies in time but also cuts down on errors and allows a common point of reference for the modelling pattern. This replaces inefficient and ambiguous, one-off representations of semantic data patterns created by hand. Presented in a spreadsheet format, such a one to one mapping represents a simple recipe for putting into actual development.

For the implementation step, we chose to use declarative mapping techniques. This phase is typically where the connection between the planned semantic data transform, the original data and the implemented semantic data plan start to diverge. Because data creators, conceptual modellers, and developers tend to work with different conceptual problems and with different fundamental tool sets, there is a strong potential for simple human miscomprehension as the data transformation plan passes from one individual or group of individuals to the other. This phase of the mapping is susceptible to these factors especially when developers use data mapping and transformation technologies that are opaque to the data creators and conceptual modellers. This creates a black box situation where the input and output control of the data transformation are known only to the developer, the data meaning largely known by the data creator and the semantic target model largely by the conceptual modeller. Declarative data mapping is a technique that limits this problem. It relies on writing out the data transformation rules in a neutral but machine readable format that explicitly allows one to read the input data source, the target semantic data model pattern and any rules affecting the transformation. In this way a common mapping data object is made that can be shared and discussed between all parties.

Tooling

With the above two phase approach in mind we adopted the following tools.

- Zellij for Conceptual Mapping
- X3ML Mapping Language and 3M Mapping Database for Implemented Mappings

Title	HRID	Author	Status	Date Created	Date Modified	Coverage	User
Bibliographic Entity Model [Census Official On-going-XMLEditor]	338448	Denitsa Nenova	In Progress	Thu Sep 08 2022 13:38	Thu Sep 08 2022 16:49		
Images Model [Census Official On-going-XMLEdited]	613174	Denitsa Nenova	In Progress	Thu Sep 08 2022 13:39	Thu Sep 08 2022 13:57		
Location Model [Census Official On-going-XMLEdited]	549927	Denitsa Nenova	In Progress	Thu Sep 08 2022 13:40	Thu Sep 08 2022 13:55		
Monument Model [Census Official On-going-XMLEdited]	207916	Denitsa Nenova	In Progress	Thu Sep 08 2022 14:59	Thu Sep 08 2022 16:50		
Document Model [Census Official On-going-XMLEdited]	629602	Denitsa Nenova	In Progress	Thu Sep 08 2022 14:59	Thu Sep 08 2022 16:50		
Style Model [Census Official On-going-XMLEdited]	810994	Denitsa Nenova	In Progress	Thu Sep 08 2022 14:59	Thu Sep 08 2022 16:50		
Census Period [Official On-Going-XMLEdited]	374373	Denitsa Nenova	In Progress	Thu Sep 08 2022 15:00	Thu Sep 08 2022 16:48		

Figure 3. List of Census maps using 3m mapping tool

For the execution of the conceptual mappings we adopted the Zellij semantic modelling platform, extending it with a new data structure for executing the conceptual mappings. We exported the data schema information from the Census database, FYLR, and imported it into a mapping table in Zellij. The mapping table's primary function is to facilitate the one to one correlation of a field from the source system to the target semantic data model. The FYLR data source is a relational database with main tables supported by infinitely nestable support tables that enable the elaboration of a highly customised and accurate data structure. This data management strategy made the mapping of a 1:1 relation between the source and the semantic target simple. Each main model in the source is connected to a main model in the target. Each subfield of the main model is correlated to a field in the target. In the process of carrying out the mapping, close contact between the Census data owners and the Conceptual Modellers was necessary in order both to understand the meaning and function of different data points but also to discover which fields were and were not relevant for entry into the mapping phase. This process led iteratively to a conceptual map for the Census data to the new Semantic Census SRDMs which could be isolated into different views and shared to the executing implemented data map developer. These conceptual maps can be seen [here](#).

To address the issue of making the implemented mapping transparent and a common object of conversation, the decision was made to use the X3ML mapping language⁷. This mapping language allows for an explicit declaration of the relation between paths in the source system and their translation to the target semantic data model structure in a way which is both human readable and machine executable. The conceptual mappings in Zellij were transferred to the implementing data mapper⁸. The conceptual data maps gave the semantic recipes to implement the data mapping on output sample data from FYLR. For each output model of FYLR an X3ML mapping file was created providing a map guiding its transformation to Semantic Census.

⁷ <https://github.com/isl/x3ml/blob/master/docs/x3ml-language.md>

⁸ <https://github.com/isl/x3ml>

Figure 4. Document model, mapping part within 3m

In this process a key decision for the longevity and understandability of the resultant RDF data is the decision of URI and label policy. URIs are the unique identifiers within a semantic network which enable the identification of a unique real world item of conversation. Such items depend on the semantic network created but can range from the URI identifying a monument, to a document mentioning it, to the name of the monument, a person, a period etc. Having a consistent and comprehensive URI scheme ensures the future stability of reference to data in the semantic network. To support the implemented data mapping a comprehensive policy to this end had to be decided. The basic logic of the URI scheme devised for this project is as follows.

Firstly, a basic namespace is declared:

`https://semantic.census.de/`

Main URI types are devised according to the high level categories of the CIDOC CRM, dividing the kinds of entities referred to. Each of these entity classes is considered a first class entity and two potential algorithms for generating their URIs are declared. Where the entity has a unique identifier from the source system, the algorithm is to insert the unique ID at the end of the URI; where there is no unique ID, a string from the source is hashed and appended to the URI to generate a unique identifier. This looks like this:

Entity Class	Namespace	Slug	Source Unique ID	Generated Unique ID
Event	<code>https://semantic.census.de/</code>	<code>event/</code>	123	123-123-123
Place	<code>https://semantic.census.de/</code>	<code>place/</code>	123	123-123-123

Physical Thing	https://semantic.census.de/	physicalthing/	123	123-123-123
Concept	https://semantic.census.de/	concept/	123	123-123-123
Actor	https://semantic.census.de/	actor/	123	123-123-123
Type	https://semantic.census.de/	type/	123	123-123-123

Table 2. Census URI Patterns

For each of the main types of entity class a further system of URI definitions is derived in order to handle the declaration of URIs for entities relative to a base class of documentation.

Using the conceptual mapping definitions, and this URI policy described above, seven mapping profiles from FYLR Census data were created. These mapping files were then stored in the associated 3M system.

3M is a database and mapping development infrastructure which supports X3ML and allows the creation of X3ML mappings in a user interface that is accessible to both end users and to developers⁹. This system allows for a means to store, create, share and review the X3ML declarative mapping definition files. The system allowed for a continuous feedback process between the conceptual modelling team and the data curators to ensure the coverage and accuracy of the semantic data mappings being produced. The use of this technology enables a continuous check back on the quality of the data mapping as it is being generated. Regular meetings were organised to demonstrate the mapping, to run it and to explore its results using the built in RDF Visualizer software which enables the visualisation and exploration of sample subsets of data.

Figure 5. RDF Visualizer, Census Person Model

⁹ <https://gitlab.isl.ics.forth.gr/ccl/3m-docker>

Initially, the project reused the infrastructure of the Ariadne+ project¹⁰, of which the Census is a member organisation, which had installed a common 3M infrastructure. As part of the pipeline development it was also decided to install an instance specifically for the Census project. The 3M instance installed for Semantic Census is hosted on AWS and uses the latest version of the software which has been significantly rewritten for performance and usability.

Conclusion

Separating a conceptual from an implemented semantic data mapping enabled the maximal reuse of the conceptual modelling done in the first step of the pipeline and the creation of a robust documentation for the target model. The declarative data mapping language and its implementation in the 3M platform created the correct link between the transformation developer and the researchers to ensure a quality control process on the mapping as it was elaborated. The use of X3ML also ensures that the mappings created for Census, while unique to the FYLR model, can be used as paradigmatic mappings by other projects who may wish to integrate their data to the documentation Semantic Census target models.

¹⁰ <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Extract, Transform and Load

The final step of a semantic pipeline working on extant data is to use the products generated in the previous steps of creating a documented target model and creating explicit, reusable semantic mappings is to use these in an ETL (extract transform and load) process.

Insofar as the previous steps are well carried out, this step can be made highly sustainable. We are here at a step where we want to get consistent data inputs and outputs moving from the source system to the target model. Ensuring an awareness of the access points for each system, data formats, and data quality helps ensure a smooth ETL process. Documenting all input and output variables and tools ensures that the process can be re-run and improved.

Method

For this project, the primary target of the ETL process is the management of the data coming from the FYLR database system in which the Census data is managed and stored and its transformation via the chosen mapping technology, X3ML, into valid RDF consistent with the Semantic Census SRDMs.

The primary task for Extract then was to understand the output functions of the Census database and its data structure and create a means to create a consistent output for use in the ETL process.

The primary task for Transform was to create the repeatable mapping. The input for this was generated via the implemented mapping step and is an X3ML package.

The primary task for Load was to setup a system for receiving pure RDF. This class of database is known as a triple store and is able to store and process information in triple based serialisations.

Tooling

Extract

The main database system adopted by the Census for its data management is FYLR. FYLR is a flexible data management environment built on a nested, relational table data model which is highly compatible with semantic data modelling. FYLR is a robust application with a number of methods available for extracting data from the system including numerous APIs and manual export functions. For the purposes of this project, we created saved export routines for each of the base models of Census data. These can be generated ad hoc by the system. The end user is able to launch these export tasks at any time. They run in the background and eventually produce a data file which can be transferred to another system for processing. The XML format of the FYLR data export is highly useful for the data mapping process as it completely regenerates the table structure of the FYLR system in a

highly processable format and provides many assigned identifiers to system objects, supporting the creation of robust URIs. For the purposes of this project, the use of manual exports on an as needed basis is sufficient. In connection with a future expansion of the project to include a common semantic data space platform with other users, the use of the APIS could create an automated process to update the data from Census to the semantic data platform on a regular basis. Since the datastream would have the same shape, this would only be a shift in the technique of extracting the data but would create the same data serialisations for use in the rest of the pipeline.

Figure 6. XML export from FYLR

Transform

For the transformation, we used the X3ML engine¹¹. The X3ML engine is the data transformation software that works with the X3ML language and generates an RDF output. The X3ML Engine takes as input a source file (generated in the extract phase), a mapping file (generated in the implemented mapping phase) and a URI generator policy (likewise generated in the latter phase). It is an open source engine that can be installed on a server or locally, run by command line or as part of scripts. For the purpose of this project, it was sufficient to set it up locally. Each extracted set of XML files representing the instances of models in FYLR were loaded into separate folders. A central folder was created for the common URI policy. Data transformations were performed locally in specified subfolders for each model, making them ready for ingestion into the triple store system.

¹¹ <https://github.com/isl/x3ml>

```

-m,--mergeAssocWithRDF      Option F-stdin: --input @
                             merge the contents of the association table with the RDF output
-o,--output <arg>          The output file name: --output output.rdf
-p,--policy <arg>         The value policy file: --policy policy.xml
-r,--reportProgress        reports the progress of the transformations
-t,--terms <arg>          the SKOS taxonomy
                             Option A-single file: --terms skosTerms.nt
                             Option B-URL: --terms @skos_terms_url
-u,--uuidTestSize <arg>   Create a test UUID generator of the given size.
                             Default is UUID from operating system
-v,--version               reports the version of x3ml engine
-x,--x3ml <arg>          X3ML mapping definition.
                             Option A-single file: --x3ml mapping.x3ml
                             Option B-multiple files (comma-sep): --x3ml mappings1.x3ml,mappings2.x3ml
                             Option C-URL: --x3ml @mappings_url
                             Option D-stdin: --x3ml @
File does not exist: takin_generators_style.xml

C:\Users\jawah\Downloads>java -jar x3ml-engine-2.1.0-exejar.jar -i style.xml -x Mapping920.x3ml -p takin_generators_style.xml -o style1.rdf -u 4
2022-09-27 14:21:16 WARN  gr.forth.ics.isl.x3ml.X3MLEngine$XPathContext.validateNamespace(X3MLEngine.java:353) - Possible wrong namespace declaration. The prefix and the URI of a namespace are empty
Security framework of XStream not explicitly initialized, using predefined black list on your own risk.

C:\Users\jawah\Downloads>java -jar x3ml-engine-2.1.0-exejar.jar -i period.xml -x period.x3ml -p takin_generators_consolidated.xml -o period.rdf -u 4
Security framework of XStream not explicitly initialized, using predefined black list on your own risk.

C:\Users\jawah\Downloads>java -jar x3ml-engine-2.1.0-exejar.jar -i location.xml -x location.x3ml -p takin_generators_consolidated.xml -o location.rdf -u 4

```

Figure 7. X3ML engine

Load

In order to explore, manipulate and visualize the resulting data graph of transformed RDF data, the outputs of the Extract step need to be loaded into a triple store database. Based on the open source commitment and interest of this project, the Apache Jena Fuseki triple store was chosen. Apache Jena Fuseki is a SPARQL server, which can run as an operating system service, as a Java web application (WAR file), and as a standalone server. We have set it upon an Ubuntu instance of AWS, allowing a performant managed solution to quickly be organised. The triple store is currently being used for testing, while the complete repository will be delivered as D7 with the completion of WP6.

Figure 8. Apache Jena Fuseki triple store portal on AWS

Conclusion

The ETL step, usually a black box to the data users, becomes an explicit and criticizable step in the semantic data management step when it forms part of a semantic data pipeline that incorporates earlier steps for modelling and mapping which emphasize reusability and explicitness. In the case of the Semantic Census project, FYLR provides an explicit and reusable data export function for each data model of the source which can be reused as an import to a transform process. The adoption of the X3ML mappings and their storage in the 3M system makes the transform function both explicit and open to modification for amelioration. Lastly, the operationalization of an open source triple store solution, enables the loading and exploration of this data in a system that can easily be adopted by other projects without further work.

Conclusion

In this document, we have argued that the key to a successful semantic data project, is to consider it not as a one-off effort, but as a new way of interacting with data that puts the scholar back in control of the meaning and eventually the management of their data. This document has been written in two registers then. On the one hand, it has aimed to set out the general problem and provide ideas on solutions to these problems, with regards to the different steps in managing a semantic data project. On the other hand, it has illustrated how these problems were encountered and handled specifically within the Semantic Census project. The format of the document was chosen deliberately in order to serve a dual function. At once it serves as a report of work done and how to access the existing Semantic Census data pipeline. On the other hand, it is also written in an open way in order for it to serve as a guide for future projects that would extend and expand the work of Semantic Census by bringing in new data sources and new perspectives on the data. The document aims to serve such projects as a ramp in order to facilitate their smooth entrance into this process.

The execution of the Semantic Census data pipeline well illustrated the effectiveness of the solutions proposed here in terms of organising a series of steps that move consequently from documenting the total data territory, creating robust semantic data models as targets, generating implemented semantic mappings that reuse the semantic data models, and using ETL software that takes advantage of declarative mappings.

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